

Research Article

The Salience of Interconnected Autonomy

Chit Karan Singh

ORCID iD: 0009-0006-8378-311X

MA Lead (Education) Student, Trinity Western University, Langley, Canada

Correspondence should be addressed to Chit Karan Singh; chitkaran@gmail.com

Copyright © 2024 Chit Karan Singh. This is an open-access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract

The statistics show that one-third of the population in Canada is living alone, and the main reason behind this is their inability to maintain a balance between their work and family life. Just as they can control the environment in their office, people look to control the environment at their home as well. This leads to stress and ultimately causes them to live in isolation. To counter this issue, the stress of workplaces needs to be reduced by educating people about teamwork and interdependence. This paper suggests incorporating studies related to interdependence in the university curriculum so that the students learn the importance of working in teams. It not only teaches them real-life scenarios but also exposes them to diverse learning. In the process of doing so, they develop their communication skills which in turn is important for teamwork. The lack of such learning can lead to isolation, loneliness, and poor performance.

The Salience of Interconnected Autonomy

Introduction

The world is getting smaller and the requirement to work together is also increasing with it. In the times when everyone is striving to be independent, interdependence is the need of the hour. In simple terms, 'interdependence' means the reliance on each other for support, cooperation, and functioning. It takes time for people to learn and develop this skill, but the absence of it has adverse effects. This research paper has the idea of interdependence at its core and connects it to the present-day scenario by looking at, analysing, and interpreting the data published by the Government of Canada in 2022. The paper also suggests two simple, yet proven, methods to reduce stress in the working class, and outlines the importance of teaching about interdependence at the university level and concludes with the long-term implications if this is not implemented.

Current Data & Trends

Canada, as an integral part of the G7 - an informal group comprising the world's advanced economies, including the UK, the USA, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, and the EU (Canada, 2023) - holds a prominent position on the international stage when it comes to advancing both domestic and international priorities. According to a collated report by the Government of Canada (2022), 29.3% of the total households in Canada were one-person as of 2021, around 4.4 million people, which was a marginal increase from 28% in 2016 (Government of Canada, 2022). This indicates that a significant proportion of the population who wish to stay alone has risen within the past decade in Canada. This may be influenced by various factors such as economic conditions and lifestyle preferences.

Digging deeper into this data from an age group perspective reveals a critical age group, 25 to 29 years, which has shown a rise in living independently. In 1981, only 9.4% of persons in this age group chose to live alone but this increased to 11.9% in 2016 before jumping to 12.5% in 2021 (Government of Canada, 2022).

This is not confined to Canada; a similar trend was found in other countries as well. The number of one-person households in Australia rose to 27% in 2006 from 8% in 1946 and was expected to reach 34% in 2021 (Hughes, 2013). Likewise, the percentage of people living alone in the United States was 25% in the year 2000 and it was only 7.7% in 1940 (Hughes, 2013).

Analysis & Interpretation

The increasing percentages of one-person housing, along with the age group of 25 to 29 especially in Canada, over the years highlight a noticeable societal trend of either making a conscious choice to live independently, finding themselves in one-person households, or being forced into.

Research by Hughes (2013) found that one of the key reasons behind the decision to live alone was the incompatibility of work & family. To stay organized in their life outside the home, people felt the need to control their domestic environment too. The research also points out that people who lived alone felt that it was difficult to share their space with family when compared to living alone since they could control all the work-related variables both inside and outside their office.

According to Boreham (2004), another possible reason behind people's choice of living alone is the 'individualization theory' where people in the modern world are forced to keep their personal lives free to remain available for work. This illustrates that people who live alone may not do so by choice but by force. This is exemplified by a recent journal published by Rudzi and

Ikmal (2023) that talks about the constant pressure felt by employees to stay on standby for work-related messages even after their working hours have ended. The chores of a family would be considered an obstruction, and the employees would resort to staying alone instead.

These research findings indicate that people find it hard to maintain a working relationship between their personal and professional lives. The amount of stress resulting from work pressure adds to personal pressures such as the responsibility of a family and managing finances (Wicke & Nelson, 2021). In such cases, people either give up or resort to staying alone so they can focus on their careers only, without any family ties.

Remedial Actions

Since one of the major reasons for people choosing to live alone is stress-related work, it opens the need to reduce stress at workplaces for people to feel at ease while juggling between work and family. A leader plays an important role in setting up the rules in an organisation, especially those that are related to after-hours work messaging and team building.

One effective technique suggested by Barber et al., (2023) is the framework of Optimal Work Availability (OWA) which creates collaborative guidelines for the online availability of the teams. One of the first principles of OWA is aimed towards reducing the urgency in responding to a message after work hours. Once an employee has reached home, their time is no longer governed by the rules of the office, therefore, they should have the flexibility to respond when and how to respond to the messages from the team.

According to recent research by D'Oliveira (2023), the level of company isolation reduced as they increased the interdependence of the tasks. From the lens of work-related stress, when the tasks can be formulated in ways to involve multiple teams (or members), they are

required to work together as a single unit, and not in isolation. This results in higher job satisfaction and eventually reduced stress levels in the organisation.

Implementation and Importance

So far, this paper has discussed how interdependence can lead to lower stress levels, which in turn would help people to maintain a work-life balance. It is also important to educate people about this topic at an early stage since they will get ready for the challenging times ahead. The best way would be to incorporate this along with the university and college curriculums where the students are taught to be ‘interdependently independent’.

- **Real World Scenario:** As the world is getting complex, the skills required to survive include both problem-solving and teamwork (Goltz, et al., 2008). The curriculum involving working together to solve real-world problems has been proposed by the authors since the problems outside the classroom are generally unstructured and involve the efforts of the entire team rather than an individual. The students should be coached on how to overcome their fear of open communication and constructive conflict within their team.
- **Diverse Learning:** While growing up as individuals and learning to be interdependent on others, the students experience diversified learning in the form of cultural diversity. A team of volunteer students from the University of South Alabama spent a week in Trinidad, where they reportedly acquired interprofessional core competencies, including ethics, values, roles, and responsibilities (Fell et al., 2019).
- **Communication Skills:** As university students are very near to their employment, the skill-building of interdependence also equips them with communication skills. There is a significant connection between students engaging in simulated training and improved

communication within an interprofessional setting (Nieuwoudt, et al., 2021). According to their research, the development of interprofessional communication and teamwork skills stood out as direct results of the involvement of students in simulation training for clinics.

Long Term Implications

The 21st Century required the pupils to be independent and interdependent at the same time. If people are not equipped with this, it can lead to several long-term implications.

- **Social Isolation and Loneliness:** In his book 'Bowling Alone', Putnam (2000) emphasises the importance of networks of relationships and social bonds within a community. According to this book, working alone may contribute to a sense of isolation which can potentially impact community connections.
- **Poor Performance:** Without learning to work in a team, skills like collaboration and coordination remain underdeveloped. This is detrimental to the overall performance of a team. A study by (O'Connor, et al., 2016) shows that the patients were at a considerable risk since there was no effective coordination between the nurses and junior doctors. The education system needs to understand the importance of teaching students the nuances of teamwork at an early age so that they can grow up to become better team players.

Conclusion

To recapitulate, it is a multi-level approach where people are unable to balance their work and family life as they consistently strive to recreate their work environment control in their after-work hours as well. The skill of interdependence in this autonomous world is crucial and it has multi-level adverse effects which range from immediate stress to inability to live in a family environment. This skill should be taught at the university for the students to practice and get

better at it. Going through the education system incorporated with interdependence has benefits, which in turn fuel teamwork.

Implications for Future Research

For the university system to incorporate interdependence in its curriculum, easy and robust methodologies need to be researched and developed. Would the current team building activities such as real-life examples, cultural exchanges, and workshops sufficient or do we need to incorporate more new age ideas like virtual reality team games and survival scenario-based team activities?

References

- Barber, L. K., Kuykendall, L. E., & Santuzzi, A. M. (2023). How managers can reduce “always on” work stress in teams: An optimal work availability framework. *Organizational Dynamics*, 52(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2023.100992>
- Boreham, N. (2004). A Theory of Collective Competence: Challenging the Neo-Liberal Individualisation of Performance at Work. *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 52(1), 5–17.
- Putnma, R. (2000). *Bowling alone*. Simon & Schuster.
- Canada, G. A. (2023, July 19). *Government of Canada*. GAC. https://www.international.gc.ca/world-monde/international_relations-relations_internationales/g7/index.aspx?lang=eng
- D’Oliveira, T. C., & Persico, L. (2023). Workplace isolation, loneliness and wellbeing at work: The mediating role of task interdependence and supportive behaviours. *Applied Ergonomics*, 106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2022.103894>
- Fell, D. W., Kennedy, E., & Day, J. M. (2019). Mixed methods study: a one-week international service project enhances healthcare competencies. *Journal of Interprofessional Care*, 33(5), 437–445. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13561820.2018.1544547>
- Goltz, S. M., Hietapelto, A. B., Reinsch, R. W., & Tyrell, S. K. (2008). Teaching Teamwork and Problem Solving Concurrently. *Journal of Management Education*, 32(5), 541–562. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1052562907310739>

Government of Canada, S. C. (2022, July 13). *Home alone: More persons living solo than ever before, but roomies the fastest growing household type*. The Daily - .

<https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/daily-quotidien/220713/dq220713a-eng.htm>

Government Of Canada, S. C. (2022a, July 13). *Map Icanada has the second-lowest proportion of one-person households among G7 countries*. Canada has the second-lowest proportion of one-person households among G7 countries. <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/daily-quotidien/220713/mc-a001-eng.htm>

Government Of Canada, S. C. (2022b, July 13). *Table 1 proportion of persons aged 15 years and older in private households that are living alone, living with relatives or non-relatives, or living in census families, by age group, Canada, 1981, 2016 and 2021* . Proportion of persons aged 15 years and older in private households that are living alone, living with relatives or non-relatives, or living in census families, by age group, Canada, 1981, 2016 and 2021. <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/daily-quotidien/220713/t001a-eng.htm>

Hughes, J. (2013). A logical response to the demands of the labour market? Young people living alone in Australia. *Current Sociology*, 61(7), 966–983.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0011392113489522>

Nieuwoudt, L., Hutchinson, A., & Nicholson, P. (2021). Pre-registration nursing and occupational therapy students' experience of interprofessional simulation training designed to develop communication and team-work skills: A mixed methods study. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2021.103073>

- O'connor, P., O'dea, A., Lydon, S., Offiah, gozie, Scott, J., Flannery, A., Lang, B., Hoban, A., Armstrong, C., & Byrne, D. (2016). A mixed-methods study of the causes and impact of poor teamwork between junior doctors and nurses. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 28(3), 339–345. <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzw036>
- Rudzi, M., & Ikmal, M. (2023). Workplace condition and occupational stress: an investigation on administrative staff in the hotel industries. *Asian Journal of Social Science Research*, 5(1), 52–63. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8088965>
- Wicke, B., & Nelson, T. R. (2021). The Intersection of Personal and Professional Stress in The Lives of Public Middle School Teachers: A Qualitative Case Study. *American Journal of Qualitative Research*, 5(2), 211–232. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ajqr/11388>